

THE ISSUE OF FORMING THE RESERVE OF LEADERSHIP PERSONNEL IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation The article reveals the role of management culture in achieving the effective functioning of democratic governance in government, the socio-psychological aspect and the meaning of the concepts of "personnel", "personnel reserve", "personal potential", "personnel - resource", "organizational structure" in the formation of managerial personnel reserve, the issues of managerial potential are highlighted that it is a holistic and at the same time a phenomenon with a complex structure.

Keywords: state power, democratic governance, management culture, managerial personnel, personnel, personnel reserve, personal potential, managerial potential, intellectual potential, new thinking, patriot.

It is of practical importance to develop the management culture in order to achieve the effective functioning of democratic management in the state power. Because in a system that does not follow it, negative relations such as mutual distrust, failure to take responsibility, negligence, and carelessness arise, which causes the management of state power to fall into disarray. That is why, in the training and placement of personnel in the system of state power, attention is being paid to their ability to manage, as well as to what extent they realize their morale and responsibility for the performance of the tasks assigned to them.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, said, "New Uzbekistan needs knowledgeable and determined leaders who deeply understand the aspirations of our people, who consider it a sacred duty to serve them faithfully." We will continue the personnel policy aimed at attracting highly qualified specialists who have high intellectual potential and new thinking, who are independent thinkers, who are patriotic and loyal to their people, who have mastered modern knowledge and skills [1].

It is necessary to scientifically analyze the socio-psychological aspect and importance of the concepts of "personnel", "personnel pool", "personal potential (competence)", "personnel - resource", "organizational structure (system)" in forming the reserve of managerial personnel. In particular, in social psychology, the concept of "personnel" is widely used as a synonym for the concepts of management, management, leader. Also, the concept of "frame" is used in the study of the "frame" problem in cognitive psychology, along with sociology,

communication, cybernetics, linguistics, and other social and humanitarian sciences. Also, in the social sphere, "cadre" (French cadre) represents the concept of personal content. Personnel is applied to qualified employees in enterprises, institutions, firms, joint-stock companies, banks, trade unions and public organizations. A staff is a person who has specific expertise, knowledge, and experience in a certain direction, and who works in a certain team [2]. So, as a person - a subject - an individual, he actively performs direct activities and actions in various spheres of society. Its activity is inextricably linked with creation, organization, procedures, and changes.

Personnel is a "force" that directly affects the development of the external environment and society through interpersonal relations, and it forms the basis of all sectors of the national economy. In social psychology, the "reserve of personnel" is understood as a group of leaders and specialists who perform management activities, meet the requirements of a certain level of career, and have undergone targeted training. Formation of personnel reserve is considered to have a legal, organizational and psychological basis. Also, in social psychology, "potential" - (lat. potential) means power, opportunity. At the same time, the concept of "personal potential" is also widely used. Personal potential is the ability of a person to increase his internal capabilities. The problem of potential was studied as an object of research by A. Adler, Z. Freud, E. Fromm, K. Jung, S. L. Rubinstein. According to S. L. Rubinstein [3], a person creates, organizes and shapes himself as a subject who changes his existence, determines his interaction with the external world and his activities. A subject is a person who acts consciously.

Personnel resource B.G.Ananov believes that from the beginning of the development of a person, scientific knowledge about reserves and resources is necessary for the realization of social expectations [4]. Also, in the study of personnel problems within the scope of social psychology, the concepts of manager, management, and leader are used in almost the same sense and in many cases side by side. In particular, the difference between a leader and a leader is the existence of its legal dimension, that is, the leader performs activities in an official organization, on a legal basis, and enters into his functional duties. The leader is formally a representative of power. And the leader is a charismatic person who unites the interests and goals of subjects united in certain groups, distinguished by his behavior and activities. The activity of the leader is manifested in the stable maintenance and development

of spiritual, socio-psychological standards of mutual communication and relations.

Since the emergence of human relations, especially statehood, the desire to understand management and its specific features has deepened. As a result, a number of important theoretical considerations and practical conclusions were developed about him within the framework of such disciplines as history, philosophy, ethics, and aesthetics. Based on them and with the demands of new modern problems, three independent fields of science specifically studying the phenomenon of management were formed in the 20th century. The first is political science in the social direction, cybernetics in the technical direction, management science in the field of economics. It would not be wrong to say that the achievements of these sciences, in addition to complementing each other, also expressed some opposing points of view, made it necessary to look again at the content and essence of management and give its full definition.

In our opinion, in addition to focusing on maintaining the system, protecting it from internal and external aggressions, and ensuring stability, it is also important to develop, improve, and advance the activities of its constituent elements in a certain direction. Because the people or employees are not satisfied with living only with stability when evaluating the performance of leaders and management personnel, even if attention is paid to ensuring stability and security, it is decided to abandon such policies or leaders due to the fact that there are no new changes in quality. That is why the management considers the above two issues at the same time. In this sense, it is correct to distinguish two important goals of management and define it as a complex social-organizational activity related to maintaining the existence, stability and security of the system and ensuring its development in accordance with prospective goals. Management is a complex activity aimed at orderly development, leadership means a position in this activity, a person with appropriate powers who is charged with responsibility and accountability for all processes. Leadership is a socio-political activity aimed at achieving these goals.

Management capacity is naturally a phenomenon with an integral and complex structure, consisting of relevant knowledge about management, spiritual qualities and psychophysiological foundations. This is explained by the view of management potential by scientists as a set of abilities, qualities and characteristics necessary for the performance of management activities. For example, Russian researcher Yu.S. Zensova understands the management potential of a person as the possibility and ability to solve tasks in the field of

organizing and managing the activities of other people [5], while researcher Yu. related to accumulated management experience, he says. Russian scientist S. L. Saibel in his dissertation defines management potential as a set of service-related personal qualities, opportunities, and abilities used by the leader to solve management tasks and achieve set goals [6]. According to O.F.Alexina, management potential is a set of theoretical knowledge, practical experience and individual characteristics of employees who perform management functions [7].

It seems that most scientists generally answer the question of what constitutes the structure of management capacity as a set of qualities, opportunities or abilities, but its content, that is, what those qualities include, is not clearly indicated. In some cases, the answer is based on some (mobilization, motivation) tasks performed in management activities. To do this, to approach the issue from a structural-functional point of view, that is, to determine what specific qualities are required in the performance of each task in management, remains one of the urgent tasks facing science.

According to the teachings of Confucius, who emphasized the moral aspects of management culture, among the values of management, gaining the trust of the people and ensuring order in the society are of great importance. In this regard, he said that government is the existence of sufficient food, sufficient weapons and public trust. To the question of what should be understood by state administration, the philosopher answers as: the ruler is the ruler, the servant is the servant, the father is the father, the son is the son, it is clear that for him, discipline is a value that should be paid attention to in management activities. Achieving these goals, in his opinion, requires saving resources, correcting distortions in the system, and mobilizing people to work.

In turn, the fulfillment of these tasks depends on the effective use of appropriate methods and tools, and the rich legacy of scholars is still worth studying. For example, Confucius, who firmly believed in governing the state by virtue, said that if it is governed by law and regulated by punishment, then the people will be vigilant, but will not know shame. If it is ruled by virtue, if it is regulated by custom, the people will not only be ashamed, but at the same time will show obedience. Also, the great thinker "Imam Moturidi's life wisdom, "Live in sympathy with the country, so that the people will always be with you", should be imprinted in the mind, heart and actions of every minister and every leader" [8] is relevant even for today.

If there is enough intelligence and humanity, and if they rule with strict discipline, but if the people are not called to action with the help of traditions

and customs, there is no perfection yet, he says. At the same time, according to him, people follow a well-behaved leader even without orders. The main principle of this activity, according to him, is that when people are involved in work, they participate in management without getting angry. In this regard, "inspire enthusiasm with your personal example." Don't know how to rest. Be an example to your subordinates, don't blame them for their minor shortcomings, promote worthy and capable people", are methodological guidelines that have not lost their relevance even today. Also, according to him, to be able to implement the above, the leader and manager "should have the ability to carefully observe, intelligence and, of course, moral qualities such as honesty, love of people, conscientiousness and honesty" [9]. Thus, Confucius believes that it is best to approach management activities based on values and traditions. State management with a deep understanding of them is praised as a guarantee of social order and stability. When working with people, on the basis of psychological, moral and economic approaches, activation of their voluntariness, enthusiasm, spiritual and spiritual power, thereby ensuring social stability, is considered one of the traditional values. At the same time, of course, the ideological limitation in this doctrine is manifested in a negative attitude towards the non-traditionalism required by the goal of development of management, from which it is permissible to draw a correct conclusion.

According to Abu Nasr Farabi, "in addition to knowledge, the ruler must have the following: first, the necessary strength and capacity to lead the society to goodness and true happiness; secondly, it is necessary to be able to convince people of the correctness of the chosen path to happiness" [10]. In fact, Farabi says that "it is not possible for everyone to lead others, to raise them to the level of happiness. A person who does not have the ability to make someone happy, to encourage them to do the necessary work, and is powerless to carry out this work, such a person cannot be a leader at all" [11]. It should be noted that along with the knowledge and qualities necessary in management, the thinker also reveals the law of their formation. For example, "if movement (ruju) towards knowledge of reality arises from feelings and imagination, it is said to be will... But when the movement or enthusiasm is added to pleasure after its first information and perception to the active power of the mind, then free will and a human characteristic are formed" [12], indicates the main factor of arousing will to activity. According to him, everyone should be prepared for management. This is, first, that the acquisition of good manners, good habits, and the means of the highest happiness is possible only when the best faculties and virtues are

constantly cultivated among the people, in the cities, and when all strive for the same; secondly, it is manifested in the reasoning that every inhabitant of the virtuous city should know the first source of existing things, their levels, happiness, the leadership of the virtuous city, the stages of this leadership, and then the praiseworthy deeds that lead to happiness.

Regulation of leaders and management personnel - high legal culture and strong will; distribution - information about the system and objectivity based on it; coordination - strategic thinking and systematic analysis; protection - pride, honor, feelings of belonging, will, bravery and courage; rational planning of activities - knowledge of the system's needs and reasoning; to negotiate - to have diplomatic culture, restraint, consistent position; organizational work - pragmatic activity and courage, to know the purpose of work; mobilization, ownership of moral-spiritual and ideological influence (salabat), fluent speech culture, socialization; and control relies on clear psychophysiological, intellectual and spiritual qualities such as constant attention, having a fine mind and perception, strong memory, vigilance, awareness of responsibility, honesty. In conclusion, improving the management system of public service personnel on the basis of democratic values, humanizing the attitude to personnel, treating them as a political value is one of the urgent issues of today. In general, in the conditions of democracy and civil society, it is said that it is necessary to have a suspicious attitude towards the personnel of the executive power, to control their activities based on distrust, but it is often not paid attention to the attitude that arises from the demand of universal human values towards them. However, it is through such an attitude that the effectiveness of their activities can be ensured, and as a result, the level of well-being of the people can increase, and the society can develop socio-economically and culturally. This is also confirmed by historical experiences. Therefore, in our opinion, it is appropriate to use the necessary mechanisms to implement a valuable approach and attitude to personnel.

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